

STUDIA PAPYROLOGICA
ET AEGYPTIACA PARISINA

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avec le concours de Yasmine AMORY

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AVANT-PROPOS

*À la mémoire de Raffaella Cribiore et de Simona Russo
pour qui le Congrès de Paris fut leur dernier*

L'ouverture du XXX^e Congrès international de papyrologie le matin du lundi 25 juillet 2022 ne fut pas simplement l'heureux aboutissement d'un long travail de préparation, mais surtout le dénouement de trois années de pesante incertitude. J'avais presque fini par croire que l'organisation d'un congrès de papyrologie à Paris était sujet à une véritable malédiction ! Qu'on se souvienne : le précédent congrès qui s'était tenu sur le bord de la Seine, en 1949, n'avait pas eu de chance puisque son président, Pierre Jouguet, le maître de la papyrologie française, était mort quelques semaines avant (et il avait dû être remplacé par le romaniste André Piganiol). Par ailleurs, des problèmes financiers – nous étions seulement quatre années après la fin de la Seconde Guerre Mondiale – avaient ensuite empêché la publication des actes, ce qui explique que ce sixième congrès soit tombé dans les oubliettes de l'histoire...

C'était un peu avec l'idée d'effacer ce mauvais souvenir que j'ai proposé au comité de l'Association internationale de papyrologues, réuni au Congrès de Lecce en 2019, d'organiser le congrès suivant et de donner ainsi à la capitale française l'occasion de se rattraper. Mais c'était sans compter sur la pandémie qui se déclara quelques mois après que la candidature de Paris eut été acceptée. La crise sanitaire de la Covid 19 accompagna les trois ans de préparation du congrès et fit passer toute l'équipe d'organisation par les diverses phases de l'anxiété à la perspective de devoir annuler ou reporter cette manifestation. Les yeux rivés sur la courbe des contaminations, nous étions ballottés entre espoirs et inquiétudes au gré des « vagues » qui ne cessaient de se succéder.

Finalement le congrès eut bien lieu à la date prévue, et, sous le regard du Champollion de Bartholdi qui se dresse dans la cour d'honneur du Collège de France, les participants, en partie masqués, étaient au rendez-vous en ce 25 juillet 2022 [Fig.1]. Soulagement, joie ou fierté ? je ne sais quel fut ce matin-là le sentiment qui prévalut dans l'équipe d'organisation. La malédiction, en tout cas, était conjurée.

Durant une semaine, les 328 congressistes sur les 406 inscrits initialement – la Covid en avait empêché ou découragé certains – ont pu assister à 230 communications (203 dans des séances thématiques et 27 dans des panels) et lire 14 posters. S'y ajoutaient les 6 communications données dans le cadre de la séance plénière organisée le mercredi matin et consacrée aux nouveaux défis de la papyrologie (je dois à Peter van Minnen l'amusant sous-titre de cette séance : « The Post-Papy Boom Era » !) : le chiffre rond de ce congrès (XXX^e du nom) et la période de pandémie dont nous sortions à peine et qui a accéléré notre réflexion à tous sur les impasses d'une certaine forme de modernité me semblaient propices à une séance plénière, non pas thématique, mais réflexive, s'interrogeant sur les évolutions de notre discipline et sur les directions qu'il serait souhaitable qu'elle prenne ou qu'elle évite. Jeune discipline (par rapport aux vénérables

Fig. 1. Les participants au congrès.
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études classiques), la papyrologie a toujours su s'adapter aux nouveautés, s'organiser collectivement de façon harmonieuse et se doter d'instruments de travail que d'autres (notamment les épigraphistes) nous envient. Mais l'accélération des innovations numériques, notamment avec l'avènement de l'intelligence artificielle, tout autant que la crise des financements que connaissent nos vieilles institutions ne nous garantissent pas nécessairement de continuer sur cette lancée et nous contraignent à relever des défis (intellectuels, techniques et organisationnels) et à faire des choix. Aussi est-il important que nos congrès fassent place à une réflexion générale sur les options qui engagent l'avenir de la papyrologie.

Le hasard a voulu que notre congrès tombe durant l'année même du bicentenaire du déchiffrement des hiéroglyphes qui fut l'occasion de célébrer Champollion et les recherches sur l'Égypte. Ce hasard, qui plaçait cette année doublement sous le signe de l'Égypte, nous rappelle aussi à sa façon que la papyrologie est une discipline qui, ces dernières décennies, s'est de plus en plus ouverte à la culture égyptienne en s'intéressant aux problèmes de multilinguisme et de multiculturalisme et en abordant les sources de façon globale ; bref une discipline qui se doit d'être transversale – autant que le fut en son temps Champollion, déchiffreur des écritures égyptiennes mais aussi impeccable coptisant et excellent arabisant. Les séances de ce congrès témoignent de cette évolution, initiée déjà avec de précédents congrès, et de cette ouverture de notre discipline avec des séances consacrées à la papyrologie démotique, copte et arabe.

D'autres évolutions se sont dessinées durant ce congrès et transparaissent dans ces actes, quoique ceux-ci ne soient que le reflet déformé et diminué du congrès – seul un quart des communicants ont souhaité voir leur contribution publiée dans ce volume. Il ne m'appartient pas d'en être le chroniqueur ni l'interprète, et je laisse le lecteur s'en faire sa propre idée ; c'est une des clés de lecture possible (et certainement pas la

moins intéressante) de ces 800 pages, qui offrent un instantané, quoiqu'abrégé, de notre discipline à un moment donné.

Un congrès est une œuvre collective. Aussi voudrais-je conclure cet avant-propos par des remerciements à tous ceux sans qui ce congrès n'aurait pas eu lieu : tout d'abord le Collège de France qui a mis à notre disposition ses locaux et son personnel et dont les différents services, sous l'autorité bienveillante de l'administrateur Thomas Römer et de la directrice générale des services Marylène Meston de Ren, ont travaillé sans relâche pendant trois ans pour que cette manifestation ait lieu dans les meilleures conditions. Je souhaiterais remercier aussi tous les sponsors qui ont rendu le congrès et cette publication possibles : la Fondation du Collège de France et la Fondation Hugot du Collège de France qui ont été très généreuses ; l'Association internationale de papyrologues ; Paris Sciences et Lettres à travers le programme Scripta ; l'École pratique des hautes études ; l'équipe « Monde byzantin » de l'équipe Orient et Méditerranée (UMR 8167) ; Sorbonne Université ; l'Institut de recherche et d'histoire des textes ; l'université Bordeaux-Montaigne ; le laboratoire Ausonius ; l'équipe ANHIMA (« Anthropologie et histoire des mondes antiques ») et enfin l'équipe Archimède de Strasbourg. Je sais gré à la Bibliothèque nationale de France et aux Archives nationales d'avoir accepté de faire visiter leur collection papyrologique le mercredi ainsi qu'au Sénat de nous avoir ouvert ses portes le mardi soir et le samedi après-midi ; ces visites, qui connurent un grand succès, n'auraient pu se faire sans l'obligeance et la disponibilité de Christian Förstel, conservateur en chef chargé des manuscrits grecs à la Bibliothèque nationale, Marie-Adélaïde Nielen, conservatrice en chef au Département du Moyen Âge et de l'Ancien régime aux Archives nationales, et Jean-Marc Ticchi, directeur de la Bibliothèque et des Archives au Sénat. En outre, durant toute la durée du congrès, l'Institut de papyrologie de Sorbonne Université a exposé au Collège de France ses plus belles et intéressantes pièces : que son directeur Benoît Laudenbach et son « papyrothécaire » Florent Jacques en soient remerciés.

Enfin et surtout, je voudrais témoigner ma reconnaissance à toutes les personnes qui se sont impliquées dans l'organisation de ce congrès : outre le comité scientifique¹ et le comité d'organisation² (ce dernier ayant assuré en sus la procédure d'évaluation des articles de ce volume), ma gratitude va tout particulièrement aux étudiantes et étudiants qui m'ont prêté main forte durant le congrès³, à Carl-Loris Raschel, papyrologue alors rattaché à ma chaire, et surtout à Patricia Llegou, ingénieur d'études au Collège de France, qui a su déployer une énergie sans borne et des trésors d'organisation [Fig. 2]. Je dois aussi à cette dernière d'avoir assuré avec autant de soins que de compétence la composition de ces actes tandis que Yasmine Amory et Despina Chatzivasiliou m'ont aidé à relire le manuscrit ; je les en remercie de tout cœur.

1. R. Ast, R.S. Bagnall, G. Bastianini, A. Benaïssa, M. Capasso†, W. Clarysse, P. Davoli, C. Fischer-Bovet, N. Gonis, T. Hickey, S. Huebner, A. Jördens, AM. Luijendijk, A. Maravela, M.-H. Marganne, A. Martin, F. Morelli, B. Palme, A. Papaconstantinou, T.S. Richter, C. Römer, N. Salem, P. Schubert, P.M. Sijpesteijn, D.J. Thompson, S. Torallas Tovar, J. Urbanik, P. van Minnen, D.J. Vanderpeere, E. Wiprzycka.

2. Y. Amory, J. Auber de Lapierre, A. Boud'hors, A. Bülow-Jacobsen, D. Chatzivasiliou, M.-P. Chaufray, H. Cuvigny, A. Delattre, E. Gareil, J. Gascoü, F. Jacques, B. Laudenbach, A. Le Corronc, P. Llegou, I. Marthot-Santaniello, C.-L. Raschel, A. Ricciardetto, V. Schram, L. Vanderheyden, N. Vanthieghem, A.-M. Veisse, S. Wackenier.

3. G. Bérenguer, G. Grelier, K. Konstantinova, C. Pena, A. Perrin, T. Ronflé, É. Soubeyran, A. Verbrugge, L. Villemin, L. Wenkin.

Quoique moins funeste que les années de pandémie, la période qui a séparé le congrès de la publication des actes a vu la disparition de plusieurs collègues. Au nom de l'*amicitia papyrologorum* – ou tout simplement de l'amitié –, je voudrais dédier ce volume à la mémoire de deux figures de nos études, qui m'étaient particulièrement chères et pour lesquelles ce congrès fut hélas le dernier : Raffaella et Simona nous manqueront, et pas seulement parce que nous ne les verrons plus aux prochains congrès...

Jean-Luc Fournet

Fig. 2. L'équipe des étudiants appariteurs du congrès entourant Carl-Loris Raschel, Jean-Luc Fournet (au centre) et Patricia Llegou (deuxième en partant de la droite).

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ABRÉVIATIONS

Les abréviations des éditions, revues et actes des congrès papyrologiques suivent la *Checklist of Editions of Greek, Latin, Demotic, and Coptic Papyri, Ostraca, and Tablets* : <https://papyri.info/docs/checklist#Papyri>.

Les abréviations des revues non strictement papyrologiques sont celles de l'*Année philologique* : <https://about.brepolis.net/aph-abreviations/>

Pour le reste :

ÄMP = Ägyptisches Museum und Papyrussammlung.

AOP = Archivio dell'Officina dei Papiri Ercolanesi 'Marcello Gigante'.

APIS = Advanced Papyrological Information System.

BerlPap = The Berlin Papyrus Database [<https://berlpap.smb.museum/?lang=en>].

BL = *Berichtungsliste der griechischen Papyrusurkunden aus Ägypten*.

BP = Bibliographie papyrologique en ligne [https://web.archive.org/web/20220308011812/http://www.aere-egke.be/BP_enligne.htm].

C.Ord.Ptol. = LINGER M.-T., *Corpus des ordonnances des Ptolémées*, Académie royale de Belgique, 1964 (deuxième édition corrigée et mise à jour en 1980).

C.Pap.Gr. = *Corpus Papyrorum Graecarum*.

C.Ptol.Sklav. = SCHOLL R., *Corpus der ptolemäischen Sklaventexte* (Forschungen zur antiken Sklaverei 1), Stuttgart 1990.

Cavallo-Maehler, *GB* = CAVALLO G. & MAEHLER H., *Greek Bookhands of the Early Byzantine Period, A.D. 300-800* (Institute of Classical Studies, Bulletin Supplement 47), London 1987.

CDDGB = Collaborative Database of Dateable Greek Bookhands.

CGFP = AUSTIN C., *Comitorum Graecorum fragmenta in papyris reperta*, Berlin – Boston 1973.

CGRN = CARBON J.-M., PEELS S. & PIRENNE-DELFORGE V., *A Collection of Greek Ritual Norms*, Liège 2016 [cgrn.ulg.ac.be].

CIG = *Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum*, Berolini 1825-1877.

CJ = *Corpus iuris civilis. 2. Codex Iustinianus*, rec. P. Krüger, 11^a ed., Berolini 1954.

CLA = LOWE E. A., *Codices Latini Antiquiores*, Oxford 1934-1966 [<https://elms.nuigalway.ie/>].

CPI = BOWMAN A. K., *et al.*, *Corpus of Ptolemaic Inscriptions. Volume 1: Alexandria and the Delta (Nos. 1-206). Part I: Greek, Bilingual, and Trilingual Inscriptions from Egypt* (Oxford Studies in Ancient Documents), Oxford – New York 2021.

CPF = *Corpus dei papiri filosofici greci e latini*, Firenze 1989-.

CPJ = *Corpus Papyrorum Judaicarum*, Cambridge (MA) 1957-2020.

CPP = Corpus of Paraliterary Papyri [<https://relicta.org/cpp/>].

- CTh* = *Theodosiani libri XVI cum constitutionibus sirmondianis et leges novellae ad theodosianum pertinentes*, ed. Th. Mommsen & P. M. Meyer, Berolini 1905.
- DCLP = Digital Corpus of Literary Papyri [<https://papyri.info/browse/dclp/>].
- DDbDP = The Duke Databank of Documentary Papyri [<https://papyri.info/browse/ddbdp/>].
- DN* = *Demotisches Namenbuch*, ed. E. Lüddeckens & H.J. Thissen, Wiesbaden 1980-2000.
- DTA* = AUDOLLENT A., *Defixionum tabellae quotquot innotuerunt, tam in Graecis Orientis quam in totius Occidentis partibus praeter Atticas in corpore inscriptionum atticarum editas*, Luteciae Parisiorum 1904.
- GEMF* = FARAONE C. & TORALLAR TOVAR S., *Greek and Egyptian Magical Formularies : Text and Translation*, I, Berkeley 2022.
- GMP* = *Greek Medical Papyri*, ed. I. Andorlini, Firenze 2001-2009.
- GMPT* = BETZ H. D., *The Greek Magical Papyri in Translation, Including the Demotic Spells*, 2nd ed., Chicago 1992.
- HGV = Heidelberger Gesamtverzeichnis der griechischen Papyrusurkunden aus Ägypten, directed by D. Hagedorn [<http://aquila.zaw.uni-heidelberg.de/>].
- HV* = *Herculanensium voluminum quae supersunt*, I-XI, Neapoli 1793-1855.
- HV²* = *Herculanensium voluminum quae supersunt, collectio altera*, I-XI, Neapoli 1862-1876.
- I.Delta* = BERNAND A., *Le Delta égyptien d'après les textes grecs*, Le Caire 1970.
- I.KoKo* = BERNAND A., *De Koptos à Kosseir*, Leiden 1972.
- I.Louvre* = BERNAND É., *Inscriptions grecques d'Égypte et de Nubie au musée du Louvre*, Paris 1992.
- I.Memnonion* = PERDRIZET P. & LEFEBVRE G., *Les graffites grecs du Memnonion d'Abydos*, Nancy – Paris – Strasbourg 1919.
- I.Mother of Apis* = SMITH H., ANDREWS C. & DAVIES S., *The Sacred Animal Necropolis at North Saqqara. The Mother of Apis Inscriptions*, I-II, London 2011.
- I.Prose* = BERNAND A., *La prose sur pierre dans l'Égypte hellénistique et romaine*, I-II, Paris 1992.
- I.Thèbes à Syène* = BERNAND A., *De Thèbes à Syène*, Paris 1989.
- Kyprianos / KYP = Coptic Magical Papyri : Corpus of Coptic Magical Formularies [<https://www.coptic-magic.phil.uni-wuerzburg.de/index.php/manuscripts-search/>].
- LDAB = Leuven Database of Ancient Books [<https://www.trismegistos.org/ldab/>].
- LGPN = *The Lexicon of Greek Personal Names*, Oxford 1987– et en ligne [<https://www.lgpn.ox.ac.uk/>].
- LIMC* = *Lexicon Iconographicum Mythologiae Classicae*, Zürich/München/Düsseldorf 1891-1999.
- LSA* = SOKOLOWSKI F., *Lois sacrées de l'Asie Mineure*, Paris 1955.
- LSCG* = SOKOLOWSKI F., *Lois sacrées des cités grecques*, Paris 1969.
- LSJ* (*ἔ Rev. Suppl.*) = LIDDELL H. G. & SCOTT R., *A Greek-English Lexicon with a Revised Supplement*, rev. and augm. throughout by H. S. JONES, Oxford 1996.
- LSS* = SOKOLOWSKI F., *Lois sacrées des cités grecques. Supplément*, Paris 1962.
- MP³ = Mertens-Pack³ [<https://cipl-cloud09.segi.ulg.ac.be/cedopal/MP3/dbsearch.aspx>].
- NGSL* = LUPU E., *Greek Sacred Law. A Collection of New Documents*, Leiden 2005.
- OGIS* = DITTENBERGER W., *Oriens Graeci inscriptiones selectae*, Lipsiae 1903-1905.
- PapPal = Papyrology | Paleography [<https://www.pappal.info/>].

- PCG* = *Poetae Comici Graeci*, Berlin – Boston 1984-2022.
- PDM XII* = JOHNSON J. H., « A Demotic Magical Text in Leiden », *Oudheidkundige mededelingen uit het Rijksmuseum van oudheden te Leiden* 56, 1975, p. 29-64.
- PDM XIV* = GRIFFITH F. LI. & THOMPSON H., *The Demotic Magical Papyrus of London and Leiden*, I-III, London 1904.
- PDM LXI* = BELL H. I., NOCK A. D. & THOMPSON H., « Magical Texts from a Bilingual Papyrus in the British Museum », *PBA* 17, 1931, p. 235-287 (édité séparément avec le même titre à Londres en 1932).
- PDM Suppl.* = JOHNSON J. H., « Louvre E. 3229 : A Demotic Magical Text », *Enchoria* 7, 1977, p. 55-102.
- PGM* = PREISENDANZ K., *Papyri Graecae Magicae : Die griechischen Zauberpapyri*, Leipzig 1928-1931, rev. A. Heinrichs, Stuttgart 1973-1974.
- PN* = Papyrological Navigator [<https://papyri.info/search>].
- Pros.Ptol.* = *Prosopographia Ptolemaica*, Leuven 1950-2002.
- Roberts, *GLH* = ROBERTS C. H., *Greek Literary Hands, 350 B.C.-A.D. 400*, Oxford 1956.
- SEG* = *Supplementum Epigraphicum Graecum*, Leiden 1923-.
- SH* = LLOYD-JONES H., PARSONS P. J. & NESSELRATH H.-G. (éd.), *Supplementum Hellenisticum*, Berlin – New York 1983-2005.
- Short Texts II* = VLEEMING S. P. (éd.), *Demotic and Greek-Demotic Mummy Labels and Other Short Texts Gathered from Many Publications*, Leuven – Paris – Walpole (MA) 2011.
- Suppl.Mag.* = DANIEL R. & MALTOMINI F. (éd.), *Supplementum magicum*, I-II, Opladen 1990-1992.
- ThesCRA* = *Thesaurus Cultus et Rituum Antiquorum*, Los Angeles, 2004-2006.
- TLG* = *Thesaurus Linguae Graecae*. A Digital Library of Greek Literature [<https://stephanus.tlg.uci.edu/>].
- TM* = Trismegistos. An Interdisciplinary Portal of the Ancient World [<https://www.trismegistos.org/>].
- Turner, *GMAW* = TURNER E. G., *Greek Manuscripts of the Ancient World*, 2^e éd. revue par P. J. Parsons (Institute of Classical Studies, Bulletin Supplement 46), London 1987.
- Wb* = ERMAN A. & GRAPOW H., *Wörterbuch der ägyptischen Sprache*, Leipzig 1926-1963.

THE GREEK PHILOSOPHICAL SCHOOLS ACCORDING TO EUROPE'S EARLIEST HISTORY OF PHILOSOPHY: TOWARDS A NEW PIONEERING CRITICAL EDITION OF PHILODEMUS' *ARRANGEMENT OF THE PHILOSOPHERS*

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As is known, our knowledge about Greek philosophical schools is essentially dependent on Diogenes Laërtius' *Lives and Opinions of Eminent Philosophers* and Philodemus of Gadara's *Arrangement of the Philosophers* (Σύνταξις τῶν φιλοσόφων) [hereinafter *Syntaxis*], an extensive treatise in several books transmitted by the Herculaneum papyri, a collection of carbonised papyrus rolls providentially preserved by the eruption of Mount Vesuvius in AD 79. The *Syntaxis*, assigned by G. Cavallo to the second quarter of 1st cent. BC,¹ was possibly one of the sources of Diogenes Laërtius (initial AD 3rd cent.) and was certainly closer than the latter to 4th cent. BC and early Hellenistic haeresiographical, diadochistic, biographical and chronological compilations. Diogenes' work, which like Philodemus' is articulated in ten books, belongs to a large extent to the literature *On Sects* (Περὶ αἱρέσεων), a typically Hellenistic genre, and is rigidly structured along lines of philosophical succession. Similarly, Philodemus' *Syntaxis* looks like a blend of haeresiography, biography and, above all, successions of philosophers (διαδοχαί), another typically Hellenistic genre.² This work, which is somewhat earlier than Cicero's philosophical production and is grounded on reliable chronological sources, actually represents, besides Diogenes', the only other 'historico-philosophical' work to have reached us, in a more or less damaged condition, directly from antiquity and one of our earliest sources about the history of Greek philosophical schools. Although it cannot, as much as other works of the same genre, properly be defined a historical work,³ it seems to have generally been written with no apparent sectarian or hostile intentions.⁴ Most importantly, the information it provides with regard to the life and philosophical training of many Greek philosophers and the doctrinal developments within their schools is often invaluable and, in many cases, it is the only evidence available to us.

1. CAVALLO 1983, pp. 61–2; GIGANTE 1990, pp. 25–9.

2. On the relationship between Philodemus and Diogenes Laërtius, see, e. g., WILAMOWITZ-MÖLLENDORF 1881, p. 54; LEO 1901, p. 56; SCHWARTZ 1957, p. 466; MEJER 1978, pp. 72–4; GIGANTE 1986, pp. 25–34; GAISER 1988, pp. 93, 129–33; DORANDI 1991, pp. 92–3; GALLO 2004, pp. 211–5; FLEISCHER 2019, pp. 684–99.

3. See, against Gigante, GALLO 2004, pp. 211–2.

4. See GIGANTE 1986, pp. 28–9.

We know that Philodemus wrote a *Syntaxis* thanks to Diogenes Laërtius himself (10.3). But—it must be remarked—the name of the author and the title of the work has not so far been detected in any of the Herculaneum papyri. This notwithstanding, several anonymous papyrus rolls have been assigned to it, with varying degrees of confidence, on account of their genre(s), structure, content and intentions. The reconstruction of the work's structure was clarified by W. Crönert and R. Philippson,⁵ who have established the dominant *communis opinio*, and has been confirmed by G. Cavallo and T. Dorandi.⁶ This reconstruction, while leaving a series of questions open, includes the following books/sections:

(a) the [*History of the Academy*] or *Academicorum Index* (*P.Herc.* 1691/1021 and *P.Herc.* 164);

(b) the [*History of the Stoa*] or *Stoicorum Index* (*P.Herc.* 1018);

(c) the [*History of the Garden*] or *Epicureorum Index* (*P.Herc.* 1780);

(d) the [*History of Socrates and the Socratics*] (*P.Herc.* 495 and *P.Herc.* 558);

(e) the [*History of the Pythagorean School*] (*P.Herc.* 1508);

(f) the [*History of the Eleatic and the Atomistic Schools*] (*P.Herc.* 327).

In addition, a new reading of the final passage of the [*History of the Academy*] (*P.Herc.* 1691/1021, col. 36, 15–20 Fleischer) by K. Fleischer has proven that other sections of the work following this book were devoted to the treatment of the Megaric, Elean and Cynic schools in either the same book or, more probably, two different books (i.e. [*History of the Megaric, Elean and Cynic Schools*] or [*History of the Megaric and the Elean Schools*] and [*History of the Cynic School*]), which still remain to be identified in the Herculaneum collection.⁷ Finally, G. Ranocchia was able to detect for the first time the end-title in one of the books assigned to the *Syntaxis*, i.e. *P.Herc.* 327 (f), and to read the name of its author, who is confirmed to be Philodemus.⁸

The famous [*History of the Academy*] [section (a)], preserved in two different redactions, an earlier and provisional version (*P.Herc.* 1691/1021) and a later and definitive one (*P.Herc.* 164), contains much otherwise lost information about the development of the Academy and its most prominent figures, from Plato to Antiochus and Aristo of Ascalon. In particular, the former part of *P.Herc.* 1021 (cols. 1–21) represents a peculiar patchwork of excerpts copied or paraphrased either directly or indirectly from lost works by early Hellenistic philosophers, historians and biographers like Philippus of Opus, Neanthes of Cyzicus, Philocorus, Dicaearchus, Diocles of Magnesia, Demochares, Hermippus, Phantias, Timaeus, Diodorus, Philiscus of Aegina, Lacydes, Antigonus of Carystus and Apollodorus. In addition, twelve larger passages, which were intended to supplement or replace the text on the recto and that are today only witnessed by the Oxonian apographs, were added by either the scribe or a corrector on the papyrus' verso. Likewise, the [*History of the Stoa*] [section (b)] hands down a mass of information on the lives and doctrines of the Stoics which is not found in Diogenes Laërtius and is mainly based on the direct witness of Stratocles of Rhodes and Apollonius of Tyre. It is a gallery of biographical portraits of Stoic philosophers, from Zeno of Cytium to Panaetius and his followers, also containing lists of disciples, anecdotes and both doxographical and characterological considerations. The [*History of the Garden*] [section (c)], instead, looks like a collection of wills by prominent personalities of the Epicurean school in Athens. The [*History of Socrates and the Socratics*] [section (d)] transmits a historico-biographical book about Socrates and some of his disciples (e.g. Plato,

5. CRÖNERT 1906, pp. 127–33; PHILIPPSON 1938, pp. 2463–4.

6. See CAVALLO 1983, pp. 61–2; DORANDI 1990, pp. 2407–23.

7. See FLEISCHER 2019, pp. 684–99.

8. See RANOCCHIA 2019, pp. 435–58.

Xenophon, Aeschines) written in an anecdotal narrative style, and providing references to biographical sources (such as Diocles, Hermippus, Satyrus, Demetrius of Phaleron), historical events (like Plato's journey to Sicily and his relationship to Dionysius and Dio) to be found also in the [*History of the Academy*], news about Socrates' disciples, and textual parallels from Diogenes Laërtius. Unfortunately, owing to the very poor condition of the surviving text, the specific subject of the so-called [*History of the Pythagorean School*] [section (e)] is difficult to be ascertained. The occurrence of terms such as 'physician' and 'nature' in it and the presence of proper names like Euryphon have made one think about a possible Pythagorean medical milieu. However, no mention of Pythagoras or other known Pythagoreans, nor of any technical term of Pythagorean 'philosophy' is made in it. The so-called [*History of the Eleatic and the Atomistic Schools*] [section (f)], though being also badly preserved, offers some valuable information about Xenophanes, Democritus, some *Silloi* (by Xenophanes himself or perhaps by Timon) and one historical figure. Besides, the sphericity of either the world or, more probably, god is discussed, along with piety (or impiety) and the divine. Finally, the author describes the public burial and the erection of a statue in honour of a philosopher who has historically been identified as Democritus.

Now, like the other works preserved by the Herculaneum papyri, Philodemus' *Syntaxis* has completely been ignored by the medieval tradition and the manuscripts handing it down are in all respects to be regarded as *testes unici*. Unfortunately, the state of conservation of the original papyri ranges from acceptable to very poor and the currently available editions of the books they transmit have largely been made obsolete by the most recent technological advances in the deciphering and reading of these extremely fragile artefacts. The currently available editions of [sections (a) and (b)]⁹ were published more than twenty-five years ago and the method employed for the latter has sharply been criticised by well-known scholars.¹⁰ The last edition of [section (c)],¹¹ dating back to 1980, cannot be regarded as a real critical edition and that of [section (d)],¹² though generally seeming accurate, contains some serious mistakes.¹³ Finally, the last editions of [sections (e) and (f)],¹⁴ though being more recent, do not contain, with respect to older ones, any textual improvement nor, as a consequence, any progress in our understanding of their content.¹⁵ Most importantly, all these editions relied on outdated tools, such as the use of conventional microscopy, and did not benefit from the introduction of Infrared Photography at 950 nm (improperly called Multispectral Imaging), which has produced in the last twenty years so many textual and hermeneutical progresses. Moreover, in some cases the sequence of the papyrus fragments, as reconstructed by the editors, has proven to be wrong and, besides, many over- and underlying papyrus layers (resp. *sovrapposti* and *sottoposti*) have either not been replaced or, sometimes, have even been confused with the ground layer. Several (even extensive) fragments were not considered at all for the text constitution on account of their severe degree of layering. As a result, the textual gains achieved by these editions, in comparison with older ones, have proven quite disappointing. This situation, contrasted with the current availability of advanced imaging techniques for reading ancient manuscripts and the possibility of applying them for the first time to Herculaneum papyri, makes it a strong *desideratum* of the research to replace these (and other) editions with new ones, paving the way for a radically innovative method

9. See DORANDI 1991; DORANDI 1994.

10. See, e.g., GIGANTE 2000.

11. See TEPEDINO GUERRA 1980.

12. See GIULIANO 2001.

13. See FLEISCHER 2018.

14. See CAVALIERI 2002.

15. See RANOCCHIA 2019.

of editing Herculaneum papyri. The ERC Advanced Grant 885222-GreekSchools, funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, has as its immediate goal to provide a new pioneering critical edition of Philodemus' *Syntaxis*. [Sections (a) and (b)] will be edited by K. Fleischer, [section (c)] edited by C. Pernigotti, [sections (d) and (f)] by G. Verhasselt and [section (e)] by E. Avdoulou.

With this aim in view, the first step is for the editors to properly reconstruct the sequence of papyrus fragments in the original roll. The methods employed in the past have frequently proven inaccurate. Basing themselves on recent studies,¹⁶ the editors will compare the circumference (*voluta*) of each fragment with J. Hayter's numeration which is frequently legible on the papyrus supports or in old apographs, in order to reconstruct the correct order of fragments. In addition, by comparing morphological elements periodically recurring in the papyrus with column beginnings or ends, it will be possible to approximately quantify the extension of the lost portions between extant pieces. Finally, by combining, where possible, these data with the information provided by the Inventory of papyri from Piaggio's time (1782), the editors will approximate the lost portion at the beginning of the roll and, in addition, its original length and total number of columns. The subsequent step will be to transcribe all the surviving text for [sections (a) to (f)] of Philodemus' *Syntaxis* paying particular attention to the stratigraphical situation (layering) of each piece—information that can only be inferred by means of accurate microscope reading. The recent use of illuminated stereo-microscopes has allowed to read more and better than in the past.

This notwithstanding, it still remains critical today to ascertain stratigraphical discontinuities and overlapping layers (*sovrapposti* and *sottoposti*) in Herculaneum papyri—a desperate puzzle for papyrologists ever since. Undoubtedly, one of the most fascinating challenges of Herculaneum papyrology today would be to detect, classify and replace overlapping layers with scientific precision and to recover for the first time the text hidden inside them, an enterprise which has never been attempted so far. The methods employed so far have been, and still remain, completely empirical. This would allow papyrologists to retrieve for the first time, or in a fuller way, many (even extensive) textual portions previously unknown to them or discarded on account of their severe degree of layering, with a major impact on our knowledge of ancient philosophy and classical literature. To this end, “GreekSchools” will carry out, in cooperation with colleagues from various physical/chemical institutes, surface profilometry by high-resolution 3D Microscopy, in-depth profilometry by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Relaxometry, and Optical Coherence Tomography on layered papyrus fragments belonging to Philodemus' *Syntaxis* in order to count and classify overlapping layers with exactitude. Moreover, following some recent achievements, “GreekSchools” is performing Shortwave-Infrared Hyperspectral Imaging, high-resolution TeraHertz Imaging and, in the case of metal-based inks (a rarity which has recently been argued for a few Herculaneum papyri), high-resolution X-Ray Fluorescence Mapping on the same papyri in order to penetrate into overlapping layers and read noninvasively the Greek text concealed in them.¹⁷ The first step of the application of all these procedures to the papyri planned for the project is to produce accurate digital maps of each layered papyrus fragment in order to classify overlapping layers with scientific exactitude. The second step is to replace virtually *sovrapposti* and *sottoposti* into their original place by means of a graphical software and to restore safely the original textual continuity of each fragment. The final step is to automatise this process through a dedicated software tool in order to replace overlapping layers both soundly and quickly.

16. See ESSLER 2008.

17. See, respectively, TOURNIÉ *et al.* 2019; GIBSON *et al.* 2018; BRUN *et al.* 2016.

Another crucial problem is represented by the fact that *P.Herc.* 1691/1021, which hands down, as we know, the most extensively preserved copy of Philodemus' [*History of the Academy*] [section (a)], is an 'opisthograph'. As mentioned above, twelve large text columns, which belong to the same work as that written on the recto and which are today only legible in the Oxonian apographs, were added on the back of the roll by the scribe and/or a corrector. During, or immediately after, the mechanical unrolling of the papyrus roll through the Piaggio machine in 1795 these passages were manually transcribed by the draughtsmen G. Casanova and G. B. Malesci. Afterwards, the unrolled papyrus fragments were stuck to paperboard through the verso and, since then, this has not allowed to access the text written on it any more. The challenge today is to recover and read the text written on the verso through advanced noninvasive techniques without removing the extremely fragile papyrus fragments from their support, what would result in their irreparable destruction. To that effect, "GreekSchools" is performing, again, Shortwave-Infrared Hyperspectral Imaging, high-resolution TeraHertz Imaging and high-resolution X-Ray Fluorescence Mapping on *P.Herc.* 1691/1021 in order to disclose and make immediately readable the large passages written on its verso. With this respect, our former application of Shortwave-Infrared Hyperspectral Imaging to this papyrus roll has disclosed for the first time noninvasively several portions of Greek text hidden on its verso and has even revealed new ones which were previously unknown to us, making it possible to partially recover this primary source for the edition of the precious book handed down by it.¹⁸ The digital images resulting from these procedures are treated by the editors as a primary source and are directly taken into account by them for the *constitutio textus*. These, as well as all the digital maps of the layered papyrus fragments analysed by us, are stored on an on-line repository run by the National Library of Naples and will be made available open-access to the scientific community.

In order to apply the afore-mentioned techniques to the papyri belonging to Philodemus' *Syntaxis* advanced mobile laboratories belonging to the CNR network of the Italian node of the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (E-RIHS) and specialized in diagnostic and recovery of cultural heritage were installed during the first two years at the project's expenses in the Officina dei Papiri Ercolanesi of the National Library in Naples. Personnel from the CNR-Institute of Cultural Heritage led by C. Miliani, P. Romano and F. Rosi are performing the *in situ* analyses and the corresponding data processing. Basing itself on the experience acquired from these analyses, this team is now extending the same experiments to other hundreds multilayered papyri from the Herculaneum collection through the same mobile equipment, in order to perform a larger investigation of many such other papyri. The goal is to disclose to both papyrologists and historians of ancient philosophy and literature a large number of new textual portions belonging to the most different papyri which were previously either unknown to, or impossible to be accessed by, them.

The Greek text transcribed by the editors from the original manuscript is compared with the already available infrared photographs at 950 nm (improperly called multispectral images) of Herculaneum papyri taken between 1999 and 2002 by a team of Brigham Young University. The reading of both the original papyrus and the infrared photographs, as well as the new Shortwave-Infrared hyperspectral and TeraHertz images, and X-Ray Fluorescence maps produced by "GreekSchools" will be collated by the editors with that of the Oxonian and Neapolitan apographs, whenever they exist. A new modern editorial system will be used, which includes both a diplomatic and a literary transcription in the original columnar format, as is standard practice for editions of many Greco-Egyptian papyri. Special graphic conventions are employed for marking, in the diplomatic transcription, overlapping layers as

18. See TOURNIÉ *et al.* 2019.

well as readings of the apographs. A palaeographical and a critical apparatus and a modern translation accompany the Greek text together with short exegetical footnotes.

Notoriously, a new critical text requires a long time before stabilising itself and imposing itself as normative among scholars. In addition, philologists and papyrologists are often accustomed to working alone. In order to overcome these problems, we intend to engage the scholarly community in a permanent collaborative review in progress of the critical editions. And this in two different ways: i) by organising yearly international workshops on one or more sections of Philodemus' *Syntaxis* to be conceived as intensive brain-stormings on very concrete textual and exegetical problems; ii) by launching CoPhiEditor, a new purpose-developed open-source scholarly Web platform on which the new critical texts will be uploaded and be made available open-access, according to the FAIR principles,¹⁹ for papyrological and exegetical comments. The new digital platform is being designed and developed by A. M. Del Grosso, F. Boschetti and S. Zenzaro from the CNR-Institute of Computational Linguistics and is conceived as a collection of strictly interrelated but independent software components. The system is implemented following the microservice architecture within a docker infrastructure, adopting suitable technologies both on the server side and on the client side. The platform allows to collaboratively work, for each section of Philodemus' *Syntaxis*, on a text reconstruction with a critical apparatus and a modern translation and, besides, the corresponding infrared photographs, the new Shortwave-Infrared hyperspectral and TeraHertz images, and the X-Ray Fluorescence maps arising from our experiments, the Oxonian and Neapolitan apographs, the transcriptions of the 'interpreters' and the print proofs for the Neapolitan *Collectiones* (whenever extant), with interlinking possibilities. This material is being made accessible through permanently open working sessions during which the editions will be revised and improved in a collaborative way and upon registration by all concerned scholars (mostly papyrologists, classical philologists and historians of ancient philosophy). The goal is to create a flexible repertory of critical texts constantly monitored by the scholarly community by making both electronic texts and digital sources remotely accessible through a single interface with advanced search capabilities.

To reach this goal, the platform includes a user profiling and control list component as well as a formal protocol to handle a multi-modal and multi-granular indexing and citational system.²⁰ The development of the digital scholarly platform is based on the use of cutting-edge methods in digital scholarly editing and is articulated in three incremental releases following the domain-driven design and the principle of progressive enhancement.²¹ This allows both editors and external scholars to start working on the texts and the related sources before the completion of all system modules. The digital texts are progressively transcribed and edited by the editors through an intelligent editor tool by following the encoding specification provided by the Unicode consortium and the TEI-XML guidelines.²² The digital collection describes all the significant data towards the publishing of a full-fledged scholarly image-based edition of Philodemus' *Syntaxis*, by taking advantage of IIIF-compliant image services²³ along with multiple levels of edition (facsimile, diplomatic, normalised, interpretative, critical).²⁴ By exploiting computer supported cooperative work and distributed version control systems, the Web platform provides the first draft of the critical text for each section of Philodemus' *Syntaxis* to be edited. The ongoing work will be permanently available for collaborative

19. See WILKINSON *et al.* 2016.

20. See CRANE *et al.* 2014.

21. See, e.g., MCCARTY 2005.

22. See, e.g., BURNARD 2014.

23. See <https://iiif.io/>.

24. See, e.g., DI PIETRO & ROSSELLI DEL TURCO 2018.

writing sessions to groups of invited or applying scholars. These colleagues will be able to state alternative readings and supplements to the critical text by means of the conceived editing system. The editor of each section decides whether to reject these conjectures or to save them along with the name of their authors by either accepting them directly into the text or recording them in the critical apparatus. These readings are marked differently, based on a few available classification systems, e.g. by colouring the text according to the scholar's name or the kind of conjecture. In such a way, the scholars immediately detect which textual contributions have been provided by whom, and synoptically visualise the textual progress of the edition. The editor occasionally sends notifications to the registered scholars to solicit their intervention on specific readings or portions of the edited text. The system manages a working session for each section of Philodemus' *Syntaxis*. This lasts from some months up to several years according to the text's extension and the constitution problems entailed by it. Once the editor deems the text suited for ordinary publication, the session is closed. The latter is reopened following new textual discoveries on the editor's part or upon justified request by a group of scholars, even after ordinary publication.

Partial editions of [sections (a)-(f)] of Philodemus' *Syntaxis*, accompanied by an introduction and a commentary, are being submitted to the new journal *Philosophical Papyri: A Journal of Ancient Philosophy and the Papyrological Tradition*, published by Fabrizio Serra, as well as other journals. A specific Website and an open-access digital repository of all publications, materials and events arising from the project has been created and will be constantly updated.²⁵ Finally, complete critical editions of [sections (a)-(f)] of Philodemus' *Syntaxis* are being issued as independent volumes, with introduction, commentary and indexes in the new series *Papyri Graecae Herculaneenses* published by Brill.

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25. See <https://greeksschools.eu/>.

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